

ISic0026

I.Sicily inscription 0026

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3526

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Res]titutori liber
2. tatis [et] f, u, n datori
3. publi[caese]ç, u ritat[is]
4. d(omino) n(ostro) L[ici]n, iano · Licin[io]
5. Pio · F, e, l, i, ç, i · invicto · Au[g] [(usto)]
6. Do[mitius] Latronianus [v(ir)c(larissimus)]
7. ç, o, r, r(ector) [p(rovinciae)S(iciliae)d]e, v, otus n(umini) m(aiestati)qu[e]
8. [ei]us

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491786
EDR 138105
EDCS 22000870

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7284 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650790>)

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Dessau, H. 1892-1916. Inscriptiones Latinae Selectae. Berlin. At 677

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